

The miracles of Eric IV Ploughpenny

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Although never formally canonized, Eric IV Ploughpenny, king of Denmark, was regarded as a saint by some. When the ageing King Valdemar II of Denmark died in 1241, he was succeeded by his son Erik IV Ploughpenny. Due to conflicting power ambitions, however, relations were strained between Erik and his two brothers Abel and Christoffer. The following years were therefore marked by civil wars between Erik and Abel, especially. The conflict culminated in 1250, when Erik was murdered by the henchmen of his brother Abel acting, apparently, on his brother's orders. Abel managed to escape any earthly punishment and thus became Erik's successor on the throne. Many therefore saw it as god's own punishment when Abel himself was killed on the battlefield merely two years later in 1252. The third brother Christoffer then took the throne. By this point, a local saint's cult centered around Erik's changing burial sites in the Danish town of Slesvig seems most likely to have begun already. The cult probably didn't really gather strength, though, until king Christoffer with much pomp had him reburied in Ringsted monastery in 1258. King Christoffer had probably tried to gain formal recognition of the cult from the pope in Rome already while Erik was still buried in Slesvig, although this was in vain. Being interested in using the cult to strengthen his own position, the reburial in Ringsted most likely was part of Christoffer's attempt to promote and strengthen the cult even more. Christoffer himself never benefitted much from this, though, dying very suddenly in 1259 amidst circumstances highly controversial. His plans for the reburial had more success, though, and over the decades that followed upon the reburial of Eric's body at Ringsted monastery in 1258, the Benedictine monks at the abbey wrote down a text that collected the many miracles that king Eric performed there. Their list of miracles were added to continuously and between the years 1258 and 1274 they recorded no less than 46 miracles happening. The pace of the cult seems to have slowed down after that, but a few more miracles were still added. The last of the 50 miracles mentioned were recorded in 1309. The text is structured chronologically starting out by introducing the Ringsted reburial and then mentioning the miracles one by one in the order that they occurred. The cult seems to have gathered much pace in the first few decades after the murder and after the reburial, especially, although by around 1309 the cult seems to have been at the end of its tether. No formal papal canonization of Erik's cult was ever achieved and high-level political interest in the cult possibly also declined at some point. When its initial strength apparently didn't hold in the long run, from c. the 14th c. onwards his cult generally seems to have been overshadowed by the saint's cult of the Danish duke Canute Lavard (d. 1131) who was also buried in the monastery church, but whose cult had already achieved that same much-desired papal recognition. The miracles recorded tell stories about people being cured, people woken from the dead etc. A notable feature of the text is that much weight are put on having the miracles documented properly by often describing their formal circumstances such as e.g. the time or the year that it occurred, where it happened, to whom it happened and who this person was, how long time this person was sick, in which way this person was sick, mentioning the names of people who witnessed the miracle happening etc.

Date Range: 1258 CE - 1309 CE

Region: Denmark

Region tags: Denmark

Rough map of medieval Denmark at the time of king Eric IV Ploughpenny and his immediate successors (duchy of Estonia not included). Ringsted monastery

is found on the island of Sjælland.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: M.Cl. Gertz: Vitae Sanctorum Danorum, Selskabet for udgivelse af Kilder til Dansk Historie, Copenhagen 1908-1912

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: [https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sanctus_Ericus_rex_Danus_\(Plovpenning\)](https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sanctus_Ericus_rex_Danus_(Plovpenning))

– Source 1 Description: Background information on the text in English

Specific to this answer:

Status of Readership: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: paper (nowadays), parchment (originally)

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: The original manuscript is not preserved

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Church

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: The text appears to have been updated as new miracles happened. As it was clearly written in Ringsted monastery, the manuscript was probably kept in the abbey church or somewhere near the tomb (or perhaps both) during this period.

↳ Tomb

– Yes

↳ Church

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The miracle protocol must have been kept in the church of Ringsted abbey where he was buried

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with restricted access

Notes: Mural paintings in the vaults of the ceiling in the abbey church

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Status objects (tools, weapons, mounts, throne, etc.)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: Mural paintings picturing scenes from the life and murder of Eriv IV Ploughpenny

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Yes

Notes: The miracle protocol was probably kept in the abbey church where the murals paintings are found also.

- ↳ Use of geometric/abstract designs?
 - Yes

- ↳ Floral or other natural imagery?
 - Yes

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Although the production of the text was not necessarily directly funded by the polity, the polity supported both the abbey financially and also this saint's cult politically, thus in a way the answer is yes

and no at the same time.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to support that the authors were directly paid by the polity, as the polity supported the monastery, however, the answer in some way is indirectly yes nonetheless.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Not only in supporting the monastery, but also in supporting his cult, although not necessarily in the actual writing process of the miracles.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: Although in supporting the cult, undoubtedly they hoped that his saintly status would become broadly recognized and in the end thus enforced by the religious authorities.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Notes: In a way the answer is almost yes and no at the same time, as there was not necessarily direct financial support for the writing of the text, but the monastery that wrote it was supported financially.

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the

text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

↳ Present part-time?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: He was never formally canonized, but locally the miracle protocol must have been considered the official recording of his miracles.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Written in latin

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Hagiography and miracle collections

Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: yes, in the sense that such miracle stories often had moralistic points to them.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: hagiography and miracle stories

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: none of the above

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– Yes

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Procession marking the reburial

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: As e.g. in keeping promises of a pilgrimage to his grave

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - No
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: Not only of Erik himself as king, but also as for several of the witnesses etc mentioned.

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A monastery

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: the abbey, in the middle ages at least

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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